

Prototype Computation of Minimum Energy Conformation (MEC) to Explore the Active Receptor Sites

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A routine computational procedure for determining the preferred molecular conformation cum molecular geometry through the minimisation of energy has been described. The method, inspite of its various shortcomings, is operationally simpler than the advanced quantum mechanical approaches. The procedure, though illustrated with a simple molecule like *n*-butane, can be extended either to the whole or to some selected portions of complex drug molecules to elucidate their preferred geometry providing a greater insight into the drug-receptor interaction at the molecular level. When applied to the well known neurotransmitter, acetylcholine, its predicted minimum energy conformation based on torsional, Van der Waals nonbonded interaction, and electrostatic energies, is in perfect agreement with the reported X-ray and NMR results. Studies on the existence of some suitable receptor sites for the anticancer drugs are in progress and the observations thereto will constitute the subject matter of some future communications. Computational work has been performed in B6700 computer at the Regional computer center, Calcutta.

STRUCTURAL and distance dependencies in drug-receptor interaction phenomenon is well known. Preferred molecular conformation of a drug molecule is immensely significant for the understanding of drug-receptor interaction at the molecular level ultimately leading to a greater understanding of structure-activity relationship, drug action mechanism and new drug design. As the pattern of essential atoms and groups in a drug molecule must have some distinct relationship to complementary features on the receptor molecule, the spatial relationship of these essential moieties may be a help to map the complementary features of a receptor. Several quantum mechanical approaches¹⁻³ like EHT, CNDO, SCF are already available to determine the preferred geometry of a molecule. On the contrary, the problem of minimum energy conformation⁴ has been approached by Hendrickson⁵, Ramachandran⁶, and Liquori⁷ independently from a different angle where the Partition of Energy Method (PEM) has been applied. The term PEM has been first coined by Liquori and seems to be appropriate for the purpose. In later stages, Scheraga and his associates⁸⁻¹¹ have not only improved the PEM, but have also combined it with quantum mechanical approaches to obtain a better picture of molecular conformation.

The approach followed by Hendrickson had greater flexibility as it incorporated the bond angle deformations and the subsequent complications arising therefrom in computing the dihedral angles. This feature has been ignored by the others as it seemed unimportant for their specific problems. In contrast to the others, Hendrickson did not follow any fixed coordinate system for the computation of

nonbonded distances which rendered the process operationally simpler, although it required more storage space in the computer memory than the fixed coordinate system adopted by the others. While Hendrickson concentrated on the problem of various acyclic and cyclic hydrocarbons, the other workers paid attention to the biopolymers like protein, nucleic acid, carbohydrates, and other synthetic polymers. According to the PEM the total energy of a molecule is viewed as the combined sum of bond angle deformation energy, torsional energy, van der Waals nonbonded interaction energy (i.e., the algebraic sum of attractive and repulsive energies), electrostatic energy, bond deformation energy, hydrogen bond energy, hydrophobic interaction energy, libration energy and looping energy¹². Computation of all these energy contributions and its subsequent minimisation leads to the minimum energy conformation of a molecule. However, the preferred conformation of a biologically active molecule need not be in the stable state of minimum energy but rather in a metastable state of somewhat higher energy lying in the neighbourhood of the minimum energy conformation. Technological advances have not only made it possible to compute energies of various conformations of a molecule, but also to view its three dimensional picture on a computerised oscilloscope screen simultaneously¹³. As all these procedures need extensive computation, various approximations have been exercised by the workers to minimise it by the judicious choice of the main contributing factors to the total energy. For example, in some cases⁴ a number of van der Waals interaction energy terms have been overlooked to incorporate various angle strain energies. Whereas in some cases van

der Waals interaction energy and torsional energy terms have been emphasized but the angle strain and electrostatic energies have been ignored. While considering a biologically active molecule *in vivo* both the hydrogen bond energy and hydrophobic interaction energy need be considered in addition to the usual angle strain, torsional, van der Waals interaction and electrostatic energies. In the present case, a general programme has been furnished enabling its broader application by an intending investigator.

The most significant feature of conformational energy computation by PEM is the determination of various nonbonded distances of a particular molecule. The different nonbonded distances are functions of (i) bonded distances, d , which are usually assumed to be constant, (ii) bond angles, θ , and (iii) dihedral angles, ω . It is evident that the geometry and energy of a particular conformation are mainly determined by θ 's and ω 's. Explicit expressions correlating these variables with energies based on parameterisation are already available^{6,11,14}. As there are six θ 's around each carbon atom, and nine ω 's around each C-C bond, the conformation of a molecule is complicated by a large number of θ 's and ω 's. But, fortunately, all these θ 's and ω 's are not independent. Thus when the C-C-C bond angle is defined (either normal or distorted), the remaining five bond angles around the central carbon atom are automatically fixed up. For a 10° deviation from normal bond angle, the distorted θ 's and their projections on the plane perpendicular to the C-C bond can be calculated by the formalism* of Hendrickson as reported earlier^{6,14}. Some of these θ 's, for reasons of symmetry or equivalent substitutions, may be identical which reduce the number of calculations. The projection angles are necessary for evaluating the dihedral angles between any two bonds.

In the present case, the practice of denoting the dihedral angle with a positive sign for anticlockwise rotation and negative sign for clockwise rotation has been discontinued. Here, the dihedral angle is determined always with an anticlockwise rotation, and hence with a positive sign. The Newman projection (Fig.1) will illustrate the point :

Fig 1.

$$\omega_{4,8} = P_{4,1} + P_{7,8} + \omega_{1,7} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\omega_{8,6} = P_{8,4} + P_{4,1} + \omega_{1,7} + P_{7,8} + P_{8,6} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

* Details may be obtained on request from the authors.

where, $\omega_{4,8}$, $\omega_{1,7}$, $\omega_{8,6}$ are the dihedral angles corresponding to the atoms denoted by the subscripts; $P_{4,1}$, $P_{7,8}$, $P_{8,4}$, $P_{8,6}$ are the projection angles corresponding to the atoms denoted by the subscripts; $\omega_{1,7}$ has an arbitrarily assigned value. By this procedure any other dihedral angle can be evaluated. It is evident from the above discussion that the fixation of one θ around each carbon atom and one ω around each C-C bond completely defines each conformation. All these points will be further clarified with the example of *n*-butane in which case the Fischer's projection formula (Fig. 2) is written first and all the atoms are specified with a number in successive manner for computational advantage.

Fig 2.

As it is a four carbon system the complete geometrical picture of this molecule is defined by 4×6 , i. e., 24 θ 's, six around each carbon atom and $(4-1) \times 9$, i. e. 27 ω 's, nine around each C-C bond. Amongst this large number of θ 's and ω 's only four θ 's, one around each carbon atom, and three ω 's, one around each C-C bond, need be specified, i.e., they are assumed to behave independently when the other twenty θ 's and twentyfour ω 's are automatically specified. In the present case say, $\theta_{1,8}$, $\theta_{2,8}$, $\theta_{8,11}$, $\theta_{8,14}$ and $\omega_{1,8}$, $\omega_{2,11}$, $\omega_{8,14}$ are assumed to be independent, and all other θ 's and ω 's are evaluated by the explicit expressions*.

The next step in getting the conformational picture is to calculate the energy of each conformation. The angle strain energy is the combined sum of the twentyfour strain energies due to these twentyfour θ 's. The torsional strain energy is calculated either as the simple combined sum of three strain energies due to the three independent ω 's or as the combined sum of three individual averages of nine strain energy terms around each C-C bond corresponding to the twenty-seven ω 's. But the most difficult problem is to compute all the nonbonded interactions comprising of carbon-carbon, carbon-hydrogen, hydrogen-hydrogen interactions, since for such computations all the nonbonded distances need be calculated first. The total number of nonbonded distances in acyclic saturated hydrocarbons is given by $N/2 \times (N-1) - (3N_c + 1)$, where N is the total number of atoms and N_c is the number of carbon atoms only. The first term actually gives the total number of internuclear distances and the second term gives the number of

TABLE 1—REQUIRED SPECIFIC VARIABLES FOR COMPUTATION

	n=8			n=4			n=5			n=6		
r_{212} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$	r_{114} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$	r_{115} $d_{215}; \theta_{215}$	r_{116} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$ ω_{216}	r_{157} $d_{257}; \theta_{257}$ ω_{257}	r_{158} $d_{258}; \theta_{258}$ ω_{258}	r_{159} $d_{259}; \theta_{259}$ ω_{259}	r_{110} $d_{210}; \theta_{210}$ ω_{210}	r_{111} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$ ω_{211}	r_{112} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$ ω_{212}	r_{113} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{213}	r_{114} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$ ω_{214}	
r_{412} $d_{412}; \theta_{412}$	r_{415} $d_{215}; \theta_{215}$	r_{416} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$ ω_{216}	r_{417} $d_{217}; \theta_{217}$ ω_{217}	r_{418} $d_{218}; \theta_{218}$ ω_{218}	r_{419} $d_{219}; \theta_{219}$ ω_{219}	r_{410} $d_{210}; \theta_{210}$ ω_{210}	r_{411} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$ ω_{211}	r_{412} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$ ω_{212}	r_{413} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{213}	r_{414} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$ ω_{214}		
r_{215} $d_{215}; \theta_{215}$	r_{214} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$	r_{215} $d_{215}; \theta_{215}$ ω_{215}	r_{216} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$ ω_{216}	r_{217} $d_{217}; \theta_{217}$ ω_{217}	r_{218} $d_{218}; \theta_{218}$ ω_{218}	r_{219} $d_{219}; \theta_{219}$ ω_{219}	r_{210} $d_{210}; \theta_{210}$ ω_{210}	r_{211} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$ ω_{211}	r_{212} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$ ω_{212}	r_{213} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{213}		
r_{715} $d_{715}; \theta_{715}$	r_{716} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$	r_{717} $d_{217}; \theta_{217}$	r_{718} $d_{218}; \theta_{218}$ ω_{218}	r_{719} $d_{219}; \theta_{219}$ ω_{219}	r_{710} $d_{210}; \theta_{210}$ ω_{210}	r_{711} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$ ω_{211}	r_{712} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$ ω_{212}	r_{713} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{213}	r_{714} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$ ω_{214}			
r_{515} $d_{515}; \theta_{515}$	r_{516} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$	r_{517} $d_{217}; \theta_{217}$	r_{518} $d_{218}; \theta_{218}$ ω_{218}	r_{519} $d_{219}; \theta_{219}$ ω_{219}	r_{510} $d_{210}; \theta_{210}$ ω_{210}	r_{511} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$ ω_{211}	r_{512} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$ ω_{212}	r_{513} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{213}	r_{514} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$ ω_{214}			
r_{515} $d_{515}; \theta_{515}$	r_{516} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$	r_{517} $d_{217}; \theta_{217}$	r_{518} $d_{218}; \theta_{218}$ ω_{218}	r_{519} $d_{219}; \theta_{219}$ ω_{219}	r_{510} $d_{210}; \theta_{210}$ ω_{210}	r_{511} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$ ω_{211}	r_{512} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$ ω_{212}	r_{513} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{213}	r_{514} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$ ω_{214}			
r_{1015} $d_{1015}; \theta_{1015}$	r_{1011} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$	r_{1012} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$	r_{1013} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{1013}	r_{1014} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$ ω_{1014}	r_{1015} $d_{215}; \theta_{215}$ ω_{1015}	r_{1016} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$ ω_{1016}	r_{1017} $d_{217}; \theta_{217}$ ω_{1017}	r_{1018} $d_{218}; \theta_{218}$ ω_{1018}	r_{1019} $d_{219}; \theta_{219}$ ω_{1019}			
r_{511} $d_{511}; \theta_{511}$	r_{510} $d_{210}; \theta_{210}$	r_{511} $d_{211}; \theta_{211}$	r_{512} $d_{212}; \theta_{212}$ ω_{512}	r_{513} $d_{213}; \theta_{213}$ ω_{513}	r_{514} $d_{214}; \theta_{214}$ ω_{514}	r_{515} $d_{215}; \theta_{215}$ ω_{515}	r_{516} $d_{216}; \theta_{216}$ ω_{516}	r_{517} $d_{217}; \theta_{217}$ ω_{517}	r_{518} $d_{218}; \theta_{218}$ ω_{518}			
r_{1311} $d_{1311}; \theta_{1311}$	r_{1312} $d_{1312}; \theta_{1312}$	r_{1313} $d_{1313}; \theta_{1313}$	r_{1314} $d_{1314}; \theta_{1314}$	r_{1315} $d_{1315}; \theta_{1315}$	r_{1316} $d_{1316}; \theta_{1316}$	r_{1317} $d_{1317}; \theta_{1317}$	r_{1318} $d_{1318}; \theta_{1318}$	r_{1319} $d_{1319}; \theta_{1319}$	r_{1320} $d_{1320}; \theta_{1320}$			
r_{1311} $d_{1311}; \theta_{1311}$	r_{1312} $d_{1312}; \theta_{1312}$	r_{1313} $d_{1313}; \theta_{1313}$	r_{1314} $d_{1314}; \theta_{1314}$	r_{1315} $d_{1315}; \theta_{1315}$	r_{1316} $d_{1316}; \theta_{1316}$	r_{1317} $d_{1317}; \theta_{1317}$	r_{1318} $d_{1318}; \theta_{1318}$	r_{1319} $d_{1319}; \theta_{1319}$	r_{1320} $d_{1320}; \theta_{1320}$			

bonded distances. In the case of a cyclic saturated system the number of bonded distances is $3 N_c$ and the expression is modified accordingly. Thus even in this simple case of *n*-butane, the total number of nonbonded distances is seventyeight. All these nonbonded distances along with the *d*'s, *θ*'s and *ω*'s required for their calculations are given in Table 1.

This type of representation has many computational advantages. The various nonbonded distances such as between the first and third atoms, first and fourth atoms, first and fifth atoms, first and sixth atoms are expressed under the specific column heads like $n=3,4,5,6$ respectively. These columns are so constructed as to accommodate more than one interaction term under a specific column head. Thus out of the seventyeight internuclear distance terms, $N_c \times 6$, i.e., 24 terms correspond to $n=3$ interactions. $(N_c - 1) \times 9$, i.e., 27 terms correspond to $n=4$ interactions; $(N_c - 2) \times 9$, i.e., 18 terms correspond to $n=5$ interactions, and $(N_c - 3) \times 9$, i.e., 9 terms correspond to $n=6$ interactions. Furthermore, in accordance with this scheme, the computation of coordinates cum distances of all the constituent members under a specific column head utilises the co-ordinate of the last member of the previous column head, e.g., computation of $r_{1,9}$, $r_{1,10}$, $r_{1,11}$ under the column head $n=5$ will utilise the coordinates of $r_{1,8}$ only under the column head $n=4$ which is simultaneously obvious from the Fischer's projection formula (Fig.2). The coordinates and the nonbonded distances are calculated by the simple recipes of eqns. 3-6 as follows :

$$x_{1,n,k} = d_{1,n-1,k} - x_{1,n-1,8} \cos \theta_{1,n-2,k} - y_{1,n-1,8} \sin \theta_{1,n-2,k} \cos \omega_{1,n-3,k} + z_{1,n-1,8} \sin \theta_{1,n-2,k} \sin \omega_{1,n-3,k} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$y_{1,n,k} = x_{1,n-1,8} \sin \theta_{1,n-2,k} - y_{1,n-1,8} \cos \theta_{1,n-2,k} \cos \omega_{1,n-3,k} + z_{1,n-1,8} \cos \theta_{1,n-2,k} \sin \omega_{1,n-3,k} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$z_{1,n,k} = y_{1,n-1,8} \sin \theta_{1,n-2,k} + z_{1,n-1,8} \cos \theta_{1,n-2,k} \sin \omega_{1,n-3,k} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$r = \sqrt{(x_{1,n,k})^2 + (y_{1,n,k})^2 + (z_{1,n,k})^2} \quad \dots (6)$$

where, *i*=row index, *n*=column index, *k*=constituent member index.

As per this scheme, $x_{1,1,8} = 0, y_{1,1,8} = 0, z_{1,1,8} = 0, x_{1,2,8}$ = bonded distance between the first and second atom recorded under the column head $n=2, y_{1,2,8} = 0, z_{1,2,8} = 0$. The subsequent calculations for $n=3$ and onwards utilising the required *d*'s, *θ*'s and *ω*'s are straightforward (eqns. 3-6).

The above mentioned four *θ*'s and three *ω*'s constitute a single set of seven independent angles. To get the complete conformational picture, each of these angles need be changed arbitrarily with judicious choice and the corresponding angle strain energy, torsional energy and nonbonded interaction energies are computed. Thus for the *k* variations of *m* *θ*'s and *l* variations of *n* *ω*'s the total number of sets is $k^m \times l^n$. The enormity of this calculation as

per this general scheme is self-evident which, however, can be simplified by some rational assumptions. For instance, to preserve the C_2 axis of symmetry bisecting the $C_2 - C_3$ bond and $\omega_{2,11}$ dihedral angle in *n*-butane, it may be assumed that $\theta_{1,5} = \theta_{3,14}, \theta_{2,8} = \theta_{5,11}$ and $\omega_{1,8} = \omega_{5,14}$. This reduces the number of variables and consequently simplifies the calculation. On the other hand, the choice of optimum number of *k*'s and *l*'s, i.e., choice of the values of *θ*'s and *ω*'s reduces the number of sets and their calculations. But a drastic simplification without introducing any appreciable error is possible in an open chain system by assuming all the *θ*'s as normal bond angles (109.47°) which renders all the projection angles as 120°. This assumption is somewhat true in all cases excepting cyclic systems and yield more or less satisfactory results. Application of the last simplifying assumption to the case of *n*-butane leads to a simpler array in terms of only *d*'s and *ω*'s. Only two variations of three *ω*'s, 0° and 180°, leading to 2³ sets have been considered in the present calculations. Energies of some conformations are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ENERGIES OF VARIOUS CONFORMATIONS OF *n*-BUTANE

$\omega_{1,8}$	$\omega_{2,11}$	$\omega_{5,14}$	E K cal/mole
0	0	180	16.14
0	180	0	6.50
0	180	180	3.02
180	0	180	5.40
180	180	180	0

To test the usefulness of this procedure, it was applied to the well known neurotransmitter acetylcholine as some experimental^{15,16} and theoretical¹⁷⁻²⁰ observations regarding its conformations were already available from the literature. The Fischer's projection of this molecule is given in Fig. 3. As the molecule contained a number of

Fig. 3

† Details are available on request from the authors.

heteroatoms its electrostatic energy was also considered in addition to the usual torsional and van der Waals interaction energies.

All the number bearing atoms were taken into calculation and the others were ignored. The dihedral angles $\omega_{2,11}$ and $\omega_{5,12}$ were varied, but $\omega_{1,8}$ and $\omega_{8,14}$ were kept in a perfectly staggered form, since all the esters were known to have the rigid 'trans' form due to the delocalization of the electron pair on the ethereal oxygen. Furthermore, the electrostatic energy favours the 'trans' conformation over the 'cis' where also the delocalization has the same effect²¹. Each of the two ω 's were given twenty values (Table 3) leading to 20², i.e., 400

TABLE 3—DIHEDRAL ANGLES $\omega_{1,8}$ AND $\omega_{5,11}$ IN DEGREES

$\omega_{1,8}$	0	30	40	50	60	65	70	75	80	85
$\omega_{5,11}$	90	100	110	120	130	140	150	160	170	180
$\omega_{2,11}$	0	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	120	170
$\omega_{5,12}$	180	190	240	270	280	290	300	310	320	330

conformations. The values of $\omega_{2,11}$ were varied in between 0 and 180° in order to avoid calculation on some enantiomeric conformations. The dihedral angle $\omega_{5,12}$ was varied between 0 and 360°. When the electrostatic energy is considered in addition to the torsional and nonbonded van der Waals interaction energies, the minima around C_5-C_8 ($\omega_{2,11}$) was obtained at the gauche conformation (60-80°) in agreement with the X-ray and NMR results^{15,16}, but, not at 180° as earlier reported¹⁷. The minima around C_8-C_{11} ($\omega_{5,12}$) was found to be at 180° for the gauche conformation around C_5-C_8 , although there were two more minima one at 70° having nearly 0.7 K cal/mole higher energy, and the other at 290° having nearly 1 K cal/mole higher energy over the minimum energy conformation. All these conformations have been observed crystallographically, although NMR suggested the value of 180° only. The energy of some important conformations are given in Table 4, while the entire conformational picture in illustrated in Figs. 4-6.

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

TABLE 4—ENERGIES OF SOME CONFORMATIONS OF ACETYLCHOLINE

$\omega_{2,8}$	$\omega_{5,12}$	E K cal/mole
0	180	2.15
30	70	1.09
40	180	1.12
50	180	0.40
60	180	0
65	190	0.02
70	190	0.20
75	190	0.50
80	190	0.92
85	190	1.41
90	190	1.93
100	190	2.93
110	190	3.71
120	190	4.12
130	70	4.02
140	290	0.64
150	290	0.01
160	290	0.11
170	290	0.26
180	290	0.48

The nonbonded Van der Waals interaction energy was calculated with the help of equation (7), where a , μ and b

$$E = a e^{-\mu r} - b/r^6 \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

are the van der Waals parameters (Table 5).

Fig. 6

TABLE 5—VALUES OF THE CONSTANTS USED IN CALCULATION OF VAN DER WAALS INTERACTION^{1,4,25}

Atom pair	a	μ	b
HH	2300	3.6	49.2
HC	4012	3.4	125.0
HN	52160	5.0327	54.94
HO	57130	5.2247	47.97
CC	7000	3.2	325.00
CN	82800	4.2403	241.59
CO	91910	4.3821	221.70
NO	86940	4.686	140.56

The electrostatic energy was evaluated with the help of equation (8).

$$E_S = 331.9 \times e_1 \cdot e_2 / D \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

where e_1 and e_2 are the point charges on the atoms expressed in the unit of electronic charge; D , the dielectric constant, was taken to be unity. The charges on the ester group were assigned from those of formic acid as obtained by the CNDO calculation by Pople²² and the charges on the quaternary ammonium system were given from C-N dipole moment value which was taken as $1D^{23}$ for the reasons that the MO calculations were somewhat controversial^{20,21} and the hydrogens of the methyl groups were not included into calculations. The bond distances and charges of acetylcholine are given in Tables 6 and 7.

TABLE 6—BOND DISTANCES IN Å

$C_{sp^3}-H$	1.11	$C_{sp^3}-C_{sp^3}$	1.54	$C_{sp^3}-C_{sp^2}$	1.50
$C_{sp^3}-N$	1.47	$C_{sp^3}-O$	1.41	$C_{sp^3}-O$	1.34
$C_{sp^2}=O$	1.20				

TABLE 7—CHARGES ON THE VARIOUS ATOMS OF ACETYLCHOLINE

Atom	Charge	Atom	Charge
C_1, C_2, C_4, C_5	0.1414	N_3	0.4844
C_6	0.2	$C_{1,2}$	0.4
$O_{1,2}$	-0.255	$O_{1,2}$	-0.3

The torsional energy was evaluated with the help of equation (9):

$$E_T = 1.325 (1 + \cos 3\omega_{2,11}) + 1.325/3 (1 + \cos 3\omega_{2,12})$$

The one-third value in the second term was due to the fact that only a single bond became eclipsed²⁴.

Computer Programming and Results :

A programme³ has been developed to calculate all the interactions taking into account the appropriate bond distances (d), bond angles (θ) and the dihedral angles (ω). Computation is repeated eight times for eight sets of ω 's for *n*-butane, and four

hundred times for four hundred sets of ω 's for acetylcholine giving the internuclear distances, torsional strain energy, van der Waals interaction energy, electrostatic energy and total energy as printouts. The programme was written iso as to compute the energies of only those conformations having all the nonbonded distances greater than 1.5Å. Some of the sets of *n*-butane happen to be identical which serve as a check for the reliability of computations. As θ 's have been assumed to be nonvariant, the angle strain energy does not arise. Hence the total energy represents here the sum of torsional strain energy and van der Waals interaction energy for *n*-butane, and in addition electrostatic energy for acetylcholine.

Discussion :

The scheme represented above is a general one having the provisions for variations of all the independent θ 's and ω 's. But instead of varying all the θ 's and thereby immensely complicating a calculation, it is more logical to vary only one or more θ 's which correspond to the substituents other than hydrogen attached to the particular carbon atoms. In the case of acyclic molecules, the variation in θ 's appear to be less relevant to the present authors. If this has been detrimental, here it has been amply compensated by the greater emphasis laid on all the nonbonded interactions and electrostatic energy which, however, have been overlooked by many earlier workers for simplifying the calculations. The general scheme represented above is applicable to the cyclic and branched systems of any size also. Furthermore, its versatility lies in the computer printout of all the internuclear distances which may be useful in locating any particular region of a drug molecule responsible for binding with the receptor site¹¹ as well as for some advanced theoretical calculations. It should be emphasized herewith that though the quantum mechanical procedure of CNDO offers a more refined approach for the computation of molecular geometry, it has also many inbuilt complications rendering it less adoptable for many purposes. Whereas the approach described here, inspite of its limitations, is simpler, straightforward and easily applicable. As the determination of biological activity itself has some margin of error, some loss of accuracy in the computation of preferred conformation due to certain simplifying rational assumptions may be overlooked. Once the minimum energy conformation of a molecule is determined, various quantum mechanical parameters like structural and energy indices can be computed with the help of Del Re's σ -electron²⁶, and Hoffmann's all valence electrons formalisms¹, the latter requiring the various internuclear distances to compute the Slater's overlap Matrix. All these are likely to throw a further insight into the problem of molecular geometry of a compound. Investigations on the preferred conformation of various anticancer drug molecules and that of the receptor are in progress and will be communicated from this laboratory in the future.

§ Details would be available on request from the authors.

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